

Management

LIFE SKILLS PROGRAM MANAGEMENT IN IMPROVING ENTREPRENEURSHIP

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Abstract

This Study at Al Baqiyatus Shalihat Islamic Boarding School in West Tanjung Jabung Regency, Karya Pembangunan Al-Hidayah Islamic Boarding School in Jambi City and Al-Munawaroh Boarding School in Merangin Regency Jambi Province.

Life Skills Program are a group of skills program that include social skill, personal skill, academic skill and vocational skill. These skills are taught at Islamic boarding schools to equip students to live independently and have Islamic entrepreneurial behavior in the face of the development and progress of the times. The purpose of this study was to determine the management life skills program to improve the behavior of students in entrepreneurship, the excellence of managing life skills program that have been implemented by Islamic Boarding Schools and determined the behavior of students in entrepreneurship.

The research approach is used to descriptive qualitative approach. Data collection techniques using observation, interview and documentation. Data analysis using Miles and Huberman models and data validity techniques using data triangulation.

The results of the study are management of life skills program start from planning activities that include vision, mission, goals and strategies for achievement life skills program are carried out through integration of subjects, semi-integration, courses, training and habituation. Life skills program evaluation includes program evaluation system, funding and teaching staff. The evaluation results are used to improve the program. The advantages of pesantren in managing life skills program include having the concepts of planning, implementation and evaluation, obtaining legality and funding support from foundation, as well as permanent funding assistance from the regional and provincial government. Santri's entrepreneurship behavior developed in Islamic boarding schools includes social behavior in the form of creative and innovative attitude that dare to take action with measured risks so as to create new things that are original and of economic value that do not violate the rules (syar'i) both of regulations relating to honor, preserving time, it is not disturb the environment, make a loss, spread hatred, persecute, give priority to help, work in faith and orient to the values of faith and devotion

Practical implications are management planning of life skills program. Implementation and evaluation of skills program that include social skill, personal skill, academic skill and vocational skill, while entrepreneur behavior is social behavior in the form of creative and innovative attitude that dare to take action with risk measurable so that it can create new things that are original and

of economic value do not violate the rules (syar'i) both regarding regulations are relating to honor, preserving time, not disturbing the environment, not making a loss, not spreading hate, not behaving, prioritizing please help, work in faith and be oriented to the values of faith and devotion.

Keywords: Management of Life Skills Program and Entrepreneurship Behavior.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Background of the Problem

The management system of Islamic boarding schools as an educational institution and religious institution often become a study of various side, especially since the emergence of the term global market era, the position of pesantren as an educational institution remain resilient in making change in an effort to adjust to the demands of the times, especially adjustments in management or management.

In order for Islamic boarding school education to still be able to exist in facing the globalization era 4.0, it must equip students with various skills education or life skills that are the skills are needed by students to be able to live independently, to the extent that life is possible, the most skill important in one side of life are skills related to communication characters, such as honesty, kindness, and responsibility.

Life skills education program is education that can provide practical, used skills related to the need of the job market, business opportunities and economic or industrial potential in society. Life skills refers to the various abilities that a person needs to lead a successful, happy and dignified life in society.

The concept of life skills in Islam is also explained by Allah SWT saying in the Qur'an an-Naml Surah verses 38-40. Based on the understanding of life skills above, it becomes very important for Islamic boarding school to manage life skills program properly so that they can be equipped for students when they graduated from Islamic boarding schools and return to the community. The management of life skills program in pesantren should ideally lead to the Republic of Indonesia's Minister of National Education Regulation Number 19 of 2007 is concerning management standards for educational institutions. The paragraph 1 in article explain "Each educational unit must meet education management standards which include: (1) program planning, which consists of mission, vision and goal, work plans; (2) implementation which includes: guideline, curriculum, calendar, structure, division of task, rules/regulation, cost; (3) the field of teaching and educational staff; (4) student affair; (5) facilities and infrastructure; (6) leadership; (7) management information system; (8) evaluation.

The life skills program management system to improve santri entrepreneurship which good and planned management is expected can improve the quality of education in pesantren, from year to

year and it can reduce unemployed. Now unemployed in Indonesia is 7.4 million or 6, 25% of the workforce, this is due to the quality of the results of the educational process in each of the existing educational institutions is not able to compete in the labor market, which ultimately becomes the government's burden .

In detail the results of the grand tour (interviews and preliminary observations) that researcher did were: 1) Al-Munawaroh Islamic Boarding School in the Lintas Sumatra street, Km 63 urban village Dusun Bangko Merangin Regency, 2) Al-Hidayah Islamic Boarding School Jambi City in an urban area precisely in the Marsda Surya Dharma street, Km 10 Kenali Asam Bawah of Jambi city. 3) Al-Baqiyatush Shalihah Kuala Tungkal Islamic Boarding School in the Prof. Dr. Sri Sudewi Maschun Sofwan, S.H. street, Pambengis Village, Kuala Tungkal, Tanjung Jabung Barat Regency.

Responding to the results of preliminary observations of research in the field (grand tour), the researcher found: (1) the management of life skills programs are still arranged in a traditionally adjusted plan with the habits in internal pesantren (school-based learning), is not using work-based learning; (2) The life skills program is implemented incidentally depend on the resource that they had; (3) Vocational skills trainers are still depend on internal pesantren staff; (4) most of the programs are planned focus on personal skill, social skill, academic skill. The component of vocational skills dominated by religious vocational. It is because of the carrying capacity such as trainer, equipment and source of cost that is owned by pesantren is very minimal.

2. Theory Platform

2.1. Management of Life Skills Programs

Management comes from the word "manage" in the form of a verb that means to take care of or manage "to manage" which then becomes "management" the meaning substantively, the meaning of management is contain elements of management activities. Based on Marry Parker Follet in Anton Atoillah management is the process of completing something related to the achievement of goals, in the finish of something, there are three factors involved (a) The use of organizational resources, both human resources and production factors others. (b) a gradual process from planning, organizing, directing, implementing, controlling and supervising. (c) art in the complet of work.

Mukhtar Latif and colleagues, explained that using organizing of management is effective if it has formulate strategies of formulation, implementation, and evaluation as well as goal achievement. Or planning goals, organizing work, providing resource, communicating work information, mobilizing and encouraging workers, and controlling the implementation of work effectively and on time. The Ministry of National Education quoted by Anwar explained that life skills or life skills can be divided into four types, namely: 1) personal skills which include self awareness and rational thinking skills; 2) Social skill; 3) academic skill; 4) vocational skill.

Life skills education program is part of education activities that must be managed well with the aim of: (1) providing a variety of job skill for people who are unemployed because they do not have the skill appropriate to the needs of the field work; (2) encourage non-formal educational

institutions to provide debriefing for people with work skill while reducing unemployment and poverty.

Based on the above understanding, it can be concluded that the management of life skill program is the art of organizing ways to achieve the goal of the life skill program consisting of personal skill, social skill, academic skill and vocational skill with the following indicator:

Table 1: Life skills Education Indicator's

Thema	Dimention	Indicator's
Life skills Education	1) Personal skill	1) Faith and devotion to God Almighty 2) Know your strengths and weaknesses 3) Self-awareness as individuals and society 4) Think rationally 5) Self-introspection and Immediately correct mistakes 6) Tough in dealing with problems 7) Ability to adapt and improve self quality 8) The ability to care for themselves such as paying attention to appearance, maintaining cleanliness, and healthy behavior
	2) Social Skill	1) Empathy and Tolerance 2) Communicative and friendly 3) Affection 4) Proactive able to build relationships and cooperation with others
	3) Academic skill	1) Able to do research as an act of curiosity
	4) Vocational Skill	1) Can use equipment 2) Obey Principles and Punctuality 3) Be honest 4) Productive

2.2. Entrepreneurship

According to Jeff Kee. Et. al, entrepreneurship is the mindset and process to create and develop economic activity by blending risk-taking, creativity and/or innovation with sound management, within a new or existing organization.

Furthermore, Harolld P. Welsch, explained that entrepreneurship is the pursuit of opportunity beyond the resources you currently control '. Another understanding conveyed by Charlie Karlsson et al, was that "entrepreneurs are individuals (or groups of individuals) who specialize in making choices that require intensive use of judgment, choices that involve unprecedented situations in which different people are likely to make different decisions.

Moh Alifuddin and Mashur Razak mean that entrepreneurship is a person who has the courage to take risks to open businesses in various opportunities, take advantage of opportunities to create

opportunities that can provide benefits, create new goods and services, create new organizations, process new raw materials, with intelligence and ability recognize and manage themselves, clever use of the resources around them creatively to create added value for themselves in a sustainable manner.

The implementation of entrepreneurship education according to the Ministry of Education and Culture Curriculum Center of the Ministry of National Education quoted by Husaini Usman and Nuryadin Eko Raharjo, includes: (1) integrating entrepreneurship education into all subjects; (2) developing curricula that provide entrepreneurship education content and entrepreneurship skills; (3) fostering a culture of entrepreneurship in the school environment (pesantren) and supported by local content.

Entrepreneurship in Islam is explained in Al-Qur'an Surah Al-Qasas verse 77 which means: "But seek, through that which Allah has given you, the home of the Hereafter; and [yet], do not forget your share of the world. And do good as Allah has done good to you. And desire not corruption in the land. Indeed, Allah does not like corrupters." (Q.S: Al-Qasas: 77).

Furthermore, entrepreneurship is the overall competence, mindset and process for creating and developing economic activities by combining a brave attitude in risk taking, creativity, innovation with new and good management, does not violate shar'i, is able to recognize and manage themselves, is good at utilizing resources the power that is around him, with the aim of gaining financial or other pretenses and promoting the principle of preserving the social, cultural and non-persecution environment. With the following indicators which table:

Table 2: Entrepreneurship Indicator's

Thema	Dimention	Indicator's
Entrepreneurship	1) Optimistic	1) Firmness 2) Not dependence on others
	2) Results oriented	1) Achievement achievements 2) Diligent and steadfast 3) Determination of hard work 4) Motivation 5) Energetic 6) Full of initiative
	3) Risk taking	1) Dare to take risks 2) Likes challenges
	4) Leadership	1) Able to lead 2) Can get along with other people 3) Able to respond to criticism and suggestions
	5) Originality	1) Innovative (innovator) 2) Creative 3) Flexible 4) Many sources 5) Versatile 6) Know many things

3. Research Methodology

This research is a study that uses a deductive qualitative approach. The focus of attention is centered on the problem of managing life skills programs in enhancing entrepreneurship in Islamic Boarding Schools in the Jambi Province Ministry of Religion, namely Al-Munawaroh Islamic Boarding School in Merangin Regency, Al-Hidayah Islamic Boarding School in Jambi City and Al-Baqiyatush Shalihat Boarding School in Tanjung Jabung Barat Regency. The research setting is in the context of managing life skills programs in increasing entrepreneurship study in Islamic Boarding Schools in Jambi Province.

The research subjects will focus on the leaders of the pesantren, religious teachers, pesantren employees, students as well as the community and users of pesantren graduates, determining the subject using purposive sampling techniques, namely informants who have more information and have an influence on the problems studied.

The instruments used to obtain concrete data that are relevant to the problem to be discussed in this study are participant observation interviews and documentation studies.

4. Research Findings and Analysis of Research Results

According to Abudin Nata there are eleven planning indicators namely: 1) Mission, 2) Vision, 3) Objectives, 4) Achievement Strategies, 5) Curriculum, 6) Experts (Educators), 7) Students, 8) Methods, 9) Facilities and Infrastructure, 10) Management systems, 11) a conducive environment. Based on observations, interviews and documentation of researchers in the field that life skills program planning at Al Munawaroh Islamic Boarding School in Merangin Regency is in accordance with the planning indicators proposed by Abudin Nata. For life skills program planning at Al Hidayah Islamic Boarding School in Jambi City, there are still three indicators that have yet to be implemented, namely: 1) the vision and mission formulated did not include the life skills sentence, but in the implementation there were life skills based learning, 2) there was no specific curriculum designed for the life skills program especially in the vocational skills component, so that the curriculum is integrated in every subject, 3) the life skills program management system is still integrated with the pesantren management system in general, out of the eleven new planning indicators implemented 8 indicators or 72% of indicators are appropriate with the planning concept proposed by Abudin Nata and Mc. Manna

Life planning program indicators in the Al Baqiyatush Shalihat Islamic Boarding School seven of them are in accordance with the planning concept proposed by Abudin Nata, while four other indicators have not been implemented namely infrastructure especially in the areas of vocational skill, management system, experts and the environment, this is because the location of the region is in a coastal area that is often flooded by high tides.

Organizing life skills program at Al Munawaroh Islamic Boarding School in Merangin Regency To organize life skills program at Al Hidayah Islamic Boarding School in Jambi City. Al Baqiyatush Shalihat Islamic Boarding School seven of them are in accordance with the organizing concept proposed by Ernes Dale, that the organizing elements consist of: (a) the work breakdown;

(b) division of labor; (c) the integration of work; (d) work coordination; (e) monitoring and reorganization.

Al Munawaroh Islamic Boarding School in Merangin Regency, Al Hidayah Islamic Boarding School in Jambi City, Al Baqiyatush Shalihat Islamic Boarding School in the implementation of life skills programs are all in accordance with Brolling's theory that the implementation of life skills education can be implemented in various channels, namely: (a) school pathways with integrated systems life skills education into lessons; (b) with a system of non-integration or special education (courses, training/internships, extracurricular). Only Al Baqiyatush Shalihat Islamic Boarding School does not conduct life skill courses or training programs because the majority of life skills programs are dominated by religious and artistic skills which are carried out through habituation.

Based on observations, interviews and documentation at Al Munawaroh Islamic Boarding School in Merangin Regency, Al Hidayah Islamic Boarding School in Jambi City, Al Baqiyatush Shalihat Islamic Boarding School For the evaluation or supervision of life skills program, it is not in accordance with Marno and Triyo Suprayitno theory that the process of controlling or controlling is done through the following stages: (a) determine competency standards and basic competencies to exercise control; (b) measure work performance; (c) comparing implementation with standards and determining deviations if any; (d) make corrections if deviations occur so that the implementation is in accordance with the plan.

Regarding santri entrepreneurship behavior in the three Islamic boarding schools which are the subject of this study, after attending the life skills education program, social symptoms of entrepreneurial attitudes are seen in the form of creative and innovative attitudes that dare to take action with measurable risks so as to create new things that are original and economic value does not break the rules (syar'i) both about regulations relating to honor, preserving time, not disturbing the environment, not making a loss, not spreading hate, not being persecuting, and prioritizing please help and it is very clear that students show entrepreneurship behavior in the dimensions as in the following table:

Table 3: Santri Entrepreneurship Behavior

Dimention	Indicators	Behaviour
(1)	(2)	(3)
Believe and devote to Allah SWT	Carry out all of His commands and avoid all His prohibitions	Seen from the attitude of the students who are devout worship both obligatory and sunnah, do not commit immoral acts when living in an Islamic boarding school independently from family and away from home.
Fingerprint	In accordance with the words, actions and thoughts	It can be seen from the attitude and words of the students who always use language and greetings that are honest, polite and in accordance with reality
Trustful	Responsible for all trust given	Seen from the attitude of the students in memorizing and understanding all academic assignments given by the clerics, as well as the students' seriousness in participating in skills training programs, such as

Dimention	Indicators	Behaviour
(1)	(2)	(3)
		agriculture, catering, computer audio video training, arts activities and other students looks very earnest and energetic.
Tabligh	Deliver and fulfill the truth	Seen from the activeness of the students in participating in preaching activities either organized by Islamic Boarding Schools or carried out by other Islamic organizations.
Fatonah	Smart in facing various changes and taking advantage of opportunities	Seen from the superiority of the students in participating in various competition activities and the development of knowledge in the fields of religion, general, skills, arts, sports, social and technology, as well as the many awards and trophies won by the students.
Optimistic	Firm and not dependent on others	It can be seen from the attitude of the students who are devout in worship both obligatory and sunnah, it is not easy to despair when living in an Islamic boarding school independently from family and away from home.
Risk taking	Achievement, perseverance and perseverance	Seen from the perseverance and perseverance of the santri in dealing with various pesantren activities both intracurricular and extracurricular such as in the fields of religion, skills, arts, sports, social and technology.
Hard work	Determination of hard work, high motivation and energetic	Seen from the seriousness of the students memorize and understand academic assignments, as well as participating in agricultural skills training programs, catering, computer audio video training, arts.
Results oriented	Dare to take measured risks and like challenges	Seen from the attitude of the students who are persistent in trying to maintain enthusiasm in themselves, such as in participating in various activities, even though they must undergo punishment and bear financing.
Leadership	Able to lead	It can be seen from the involvement of the students in the activities of organizations that exist in the pesantren, as well as seen from the culture of independent living, able to maintain and care for all of their property in the hostel and be able to lead themselves.
	Can get along with others and be able to respond to criticism and suggestions	It can be seen from the involvement of the students in the learning groups of each student learning from each other, socializing and communicating to form a social culture in the pesantren as well as the behavior of the students who are able to convey ideas and accept opinions in discussion activities, as well as in daily life.

Dimention	Indicators	Behaviour
(1)	(2)	(3)
Originality	Creative, Innovative (innovator), flexible, many sources and know a lot of things	Seen from the pesantren environment which is neatly arranged, clean, and decorated with skills created by the students, the implementation of the santri creativity stage show that exhibits various santri skills in various fields such as dance, sound art, calligraphy art of reading and writing AL-Qur; an, drama and martial arts with the pattern of the times.
Future oriented	Perspective and visionary	Seen from the completeness of facilities and infrastructure available at the pesantren as well as the seriousness of the students in participating in various life skills activities at the pesantren,
Preserving Nature	Does not make environmental damage in obtaining profits	Seen from the boarding school environment which is neat, clean, and decorated with the skills of the work of the students, as well as the creation of a comfortable environment of the pesantren environment.

Table 4: Comparative Matrix of Excellence in Entrepreneurship

Field Entrepreneurship	Al Munawaroh Islamic Boarding School	Al Hidayah Islamic boarding school	Al Baqiyatush Shalihah Islamic Boarding School
1. Services	Tahfizul Qur'an training	Tahfizul Qur'an training	Tahfizul Qur'an training
a. Religious	Da'wah /Muhadhoroh	Da'wah / Muhadhoroh	Da'wah / Muhadhoroh
	Khotil Qur'an Training	Khotil Qur'an Training	Khotil Qur; a Training
	Tilawatul Qur'an	Tilawatul Qur'an	Tilawatul Qur'an
b. General Services	Computer services	Computer services	
	AudioVideo services	AudioVideo services	
	Convection Services	Convection Services	
2. Art	Marawis	Marawis	Marawis
3. Agriculture	Palm plantations	Horticulture	
	Horticulture		
4. Animal Husbandry	Cow Fattening	Cow Fattening	
	Freshwater fish farming		
5. Trading	Mini Market	Mini Market	Refill mineral water
	Refill mineral water	Refill mineral water	
	Traditional market		

6. Industry	Non-organic waste processing	Non-organic waste processing	
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The types of entrepreneurship activities in the three Islamic Boarding Schools above are in the form of efforts to create and develop economic activities by combining risk taking, creativity, innovation with new and good management, in organizations.

The concept of entrepreneurship behavior implemented in the three Islamic Boarding Schools above includes Islamic values, especially faith and piety to Allah SWT, as well as the attitude of print, tabligh, trustworthiness, fatonah, inclusion of indicators of faith and devotion to Allah SWT. In the component of Islamic entrepreneurship there are indicators: a) amar ma'ruf nahi munkar, b) pious and authoritative, c) jihad in spirit. For the indicator amar ma'ruf nahi mungkar in accordance with the word of Allah SWT.

The entry of Islamic values into the theory of entrepreneurship from the results of this study is a refinement of the theory of entrepreneurship that has been advanced by Jeff Kee. Et al who explained that entrepreneurship is the mindset and process for creating and developing economic activities by combining risk taking, creativity, innovation with new and good management, in organizations. Likewise, with the theory of entrepreneurship put forward by Ngerem Eucharia Iheoma and Ezikpe Ngozi who defined that entrepreneurship is the willingness to take risks, develop, manage and manage a business venture in a competitive and growing global market.

5. Conclusions

Life Skills Program of Management in Improving Entrepreneurship Behavior at Al Munawaroh Islamic Boarding School in Merangin Regency, Al Hidayah Islamic Boarding School in Jambi City, and Al Baqiyatush Shalihat Islamic Boarding School in Tanjung Jabung Barat include activities: a) Planning of life skill program in improving santri entrepreneurship behavior, b) life skill program, and c) Evaluate the life skill program.

However, the management of life skills programs in improving santri entrepreneurship has not been effective enough because: 1) lack of facilities and infrastructure to support life skills activities, 2) lack of life skills trainers, 3) lack of funds, 4) government guidance on life skills and entrepreneurship in pesantren still minimal, 5) difficulties in marketing the results of skills, 6) difficulties in obtaining partners so that entrepreneurial behavior that arises in the personality of students is more dominated by religious behavior.

The advantages of managing life skills programs in enhancing the behavior of students in entrepreneurship at Al Baqiyatush Shalihat Islamic Boarding School Tanjung Jabung Barat are: a) having a plan that is stated in the vision and mission, goals and achievement strategies that are based on Islamic pesantren culture, b) for Al Hidayah Islamic Boarding School Jambi received legality and financing support from the Jambi provincial government, while Al Munawaroh Islamic Boarding School received legality support, infrastructure and routine financing from the Merangin district government. The excellence of managing life skills programs in enhancing the behavior of students in entrepreneurship at Al Baqiyatush Shalihat Tanjung Jabung Barat Islamic Boarding School, obtaining financial support, facilities and infrastructure as well as educators and

educators from the Tariqat Naksabandiyah group routinely, c) implementation is supported by Local Government policies both the Province and Regency, as well as in accordance with local cultural traditions, d) evaluation is carried out continuously involving internal parties (Kyai and Madrasah Head). External parties involving the Provincial Government, Regency Government and the Educational Supervisory Agency and their respective foundations.

Santri entrepreneurship behavior developed in three Islamic boarding schools which are the subject of this study, is social behavior in the form of creative and innovative attitudes that dare to take actions with measured risks so as to create new things that are original and of economic value not violating the rules (shar'i) good about regulations relating to honor, preserving time, not disturbing the environment, not making a loss, not spreading hate, not being persecuting, prioritizing help, working in faith and orienting the values of faith and devotion.

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